

MULTIFUNCTIONAL PERFORMANCE OF TAILOR-MADE CARBON FIBRES

An improved structural battery negative electrode

Ruben Tavano, Johanna Xu, Fang Liu, Leif E. Asp, Materials and Computational Mechanics,
Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden

Claudia Creighton, Luke C. Henderson, Institute for Frontier Materials, Deakin University, Australia

Structural batteries

- **Multifunctionality:**
 - Energy storage
 - Load carrying capabilities
- **Layered composite structure:**
 - Carbon fibre negative electrode
 - Glass fibre separator
 - Lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP) on aluminium positive electrode
 - Bi-continuous structural battery electrolyte (SBE)

Conventional and structural battery

Current collector + connector:

Copper foil

Negative electrode:

Graphite particles

Electrolyte:

Liquid

Positive electrode:

Metal oxide particles

Current collector + negative electrode:

Carbon fibres

Current connector:

Copper strip

Electrolyte:

SBE

Current collector + positive electrode:

Coated carbon fibre

Current collector:

Aluminium strip

Conventional Li-ion battery

Structural battery laminate

Pouch-bag cells

Infused and cured cell

Sealed cell

Carbon fibres as negative electrodes

- Conventional batteries use graphite
- Carbon fibres are also made of carbon but with a different microstructure
- The microstructure is called turbostratic graphite
- Precursor and manufacturing process affect the microstructure
- Lithium ions are stored differently in different microstructures

Previous work

- Lithium insertion mechanism in commercial carbon fibres has been studied
- Presence of different heteroatoms has been determined
- Effect of microstructure has been identified

Fredi et al., "Graphitic microstructure and performance of carbon fibre Li-ion structural battery electrodes", *Multifunctional Materials*, 2018
 Johansen M et al., "Mapping nitrogen heteroatoms in carbon fibres using atom probe tomography and photoelectron spectroscopy", *Carbon*, 2021
 Xu et al., "Effect of tension during stabilization on carbon fiber multifunctionality for structural battery composites", *Carbon*, 2023

Carbon fibres manufacturing

- Historically, the focus has been on mechanical properties
- This work is a collaboration between Chalmers University of Technology and Deakin University:
 - Carbon fibres were manufactured at Carbon Nexus on a state-of-the-art research line from a 24k tow of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor
 - Different process parameters were used to produce 3 different types of fibres
 - The focus was on making carbon fibres with an optimal microstructure to be used in structural batteries

Details about manufacturing

- Different temperature profiles for the LT (3 zones) and HT (2 zones) carbonization steps:

Trial	LT-furnace zone 1 (°C)	LT-furnace zone 2 (°C)	LT-furnace zone 3 (°C)	HT-furnace zone 1 (°C)	HT-furnace zone 2 (°C)
Trial 1	284	450	600	1000	1300
Trial 2	350	550	700	1100	1400
Trial 3	450	650	800	1200	1500

Manufacturing process

Physical and mechanical characterization

- Density measurements
- Diameter measurements
- Surface area measurements
- Conductivity measurements
- Single fibre tensile tests

Electrochemical characterization

Li-foil to
negative
terminal

CFs to
positive
terminal

Characterization results (1)

Fibre density

Fibre diameter

Fibre conductivity

Fibre surface area

Characterization results (1)

Characterization results (1)

Fibre density

Fibre diameter

Fibre conductivity

Fibre surface area

Fibre tensile modulus

Fibre breaking strength

Characterization results (2)

- Previous study has shown:

- Similar results are expected also for these carbon fibres based on preliminary results (cycling of the half-cells is still not finished)

Summary

Structural batteries

Electrochemical characterization

Tailor-made carbon fibres

Further analyses

- Microstructure determination:
 - SAXS/WAXS
 - HR-TEM
- Low-temperature extracted CFs characterization

Physical and mechanical characterization

Further optimizations

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